

AlSi10Mg additively manufactured anchors for a novel multimaterial hybrid joining for aerospace

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ABSTRACT

The improvement of the economic and the technological performance of joining technologies is currently a hot topic in aviation. Although mechanical bonding such as fasteners and rivets are been one of the common techniques to bond metals with fibre reinforced polymers, they add unnecessary weight, require time consuming assemblies and damage to fibres can occur during handling. These challenges underscore the necessity for alternative solutions in joining technology. MIMOSA, an EU funded project, proposes a solution to overcome these limitations: a novel process for multi-material joining of Additively Manufactured AlSi10Mg and CFRP.

The proposed joining technology exploits the mechanical interlocking mechanism between the CFRPs and the 3D metal anchors. A lattice structure is introduced to control the thermal expansion between the two parts, by reducing the superficial stress. This combined detail of design and manufacturing process is patented [1, 2], marking a significant milestone in advancing joint technology within the aerospace industry.

In this study, metal anchors produced in AlSi10Mg via Additive Manufacturing will be analyzed, evaluating their mechanical performance and the feasibility of producing novel multi-material joint structures.

1. INTRODUCTION

This study is a part of developments of the MIMOSA project (Multimaterial airframes based on 3D joints between AM metals and carbon-fiber composites. GA: 101091826) under the framework of Horizon 2020. MIMOSA Project is developing hybrid composites and multi-material joints based on Additive Manufacturing. AlSi10Mg alloys are developed with different anchors promoting adhesion and joining with composite structures. The ultimate goal of the project is to build a Vertical Stabilizer prototype with improved joining technologies that will open new paths, but not limited to, joining in aviation,.

Additive Manufacturing (AM) techniques have become increasingly employed in recent years, growing more pervasive. Among the numerous advantages offered, the significant freedom in design that they allow stands out. This opens up new opportunities for lightweighting while maintaining the required properties, as well as for creating geometries with specific functionalities. If attempted with traditional processes, these would lead to considerable waste during production [3].

In the aerospace sector, metal AM is of particular interest as it enables the creation of lighter components, reduces lead times, and allows for the decentralization of production, ensuring a more resilient supply chain, thus becoming a valid option for reaching sustainability targets [4]. Furthermore, Direct Energy Deposition (DED) technologies allow the use of additive manufacturing as a repair technique. To date, metal AM requires the use of metal powders as feedstock, but some new concepts, based on filament techniques are emerging [5]. MIMOSA project leverages the versatility of AM to enhance the coupling between composite and metal. In particular, anchors were built on AlMgSi10 structures to facilitate interlocking, while a lattice structure was designed to accommodate the differential thermal expansion coefficients (Figure 1). Creating reliable joints is essential in various fields of applications, but crucial in safety related applications such as aviation. The use of techniques like interlocking to improve the mechanical properties of the joint is well-documented [6-7], and AM allows for highly precise control over surface texture to promote interpenetration.

Figure 1: AlSi10Mg anchors specimens a) as produced and b) integrated to CFRP.

The fabrication of AlMgSi10 components is achieved through a powder-based additive manufacturing (AM) technique known as Laser Beam Powder Bed Fusion (LB-PBF); a well-known method for AM for metals. It involves the sequential distribution of fine metal powder layers on a build platform, where a high-energy laser selectively melts the powder in accordance with predefined geometries. Subsequent to the melting process, the build platform descends incrementally to accommodate a new powder layer, and this cycle is repeated until the part is fully constructed [8].

The advantages provided by LB-PBF are unique, but several challenges must be faced in the fabrication of AlMgSi10 parts. First, the rapid cooling rates during solidification can induce defects like pores and cracks that can undermine the mechanical properties of the material. Furthermore, the high reflectivity of aluminum alloys limits the absorption of laser radiation, resulting in complications in the melting process [9]. In order to avoid such issues and manufacture a high-quality part the optimization of process parameters, such as laser power, scan speed, and hatching strategies, is key.

Another advantage of metal AM is its excellent integration within the circular economy. Firstly, as previously mentioned, it helps in reducing material wastage by avoiding subtractive

processes typical of conventional methods. Additionally, it is possible to produce powders from recycled metal parts. Indeed, starting from metal scraps, new powders can be obtained through the atomization process, which can then be used again for new AM parts [10].

2. EXPERIMENTATION

The experimental part was divided in two different steps. The optimization of the printing AlSi10Mg anchors was the first step. In fact, the parameters given by the data sheet of EOS GmbH - Electro Optical Systems may not be optimized for printing components with such small details as anchor pins. Two test matrices were made to optimize infill and contour parameters to reach the requirements needed for the project application. The following step was the production of tensile specimens which were produced with the optimized process parameters. The specimens were finally subjected to various heat treatments before testing them.

2.1. Printing parameters optimization

The density of the AM parts of AlSi10Mg has been identified as a critical property for printed parts. The relative density for such applications should be very high, i.e. 99.9%. This value is to be intended as a relative density: the ratio between the measured density of 3D printed samples and the theoretical density of the AlSi10Mg alloy.

Moreover, the relative density of AM part results from the combination of printing process and post-printing processes, if any, e.g. heat treatments. Since process parameters and resulting relative density are strictly related, it is worth using physical quantities which allow to compare the output of different sets of printing parameters. In particular, the Volumetric Energy Density (VED) measures the energy input per unit volume and is described by the formula:

$$VED \left[\frac{J}{mm^3} \right] = \frac{P [W]}{v \left[\frac{mm}{s} \right] \cdot h [mm] \cdot t [mm]} \quad (1)$$

where P is the laser power, v is the scanning speed of the laser beam on the building plate, h is the hatch spacing (the distance of the centerlines of two subsequent scan tracks) and t is the layer thickness (fixed thickness of each of the powder layers). All the above parameters can be set in the printing machine software. Although representing a normalization of the energy input over a unit volume, the VED parameter is suitable for evaluating the effect of printing process on the quality of the infill of printed parts, which pertains to the core of printed specimens. On the other hand, when dealing with limited dimensions of the specimens or melting metal powders at the edges of the printed parts (also referred to as the contour), a different physical quantity could describe better the printing process. Linear Energy Density (LED) is defined as:

$$LED \left[\frac{J}{mm} \right] = \frac{P [W]}{v \left[\frac{mm}{s} \right]} \quad (2)$$

where P and v quantities are related to equation 1. The quantity described by equation 2 was used to quantify the energy input on the contour of the specimens.

Specimens were printed on the EOS M290 metal printer [11] at F3nice's facilities and used to check the density of AlSi10Mg parts. Measurements were conducted by using the Archimedes' principle; weighing the samples with a hydrostatic balance according to ASTM B962 standard.

2.2. Thermal treatment optimization

The optimized process parameters were used for printing AlSi10Mg tensile specimens with F3nice's EOS M290 machine. baseline materials were produces with different heat treatments and tested. The aim was to improve the mechanical properties, limiting the accretion of internal porosity, and simulating the expected curing process for making the joint with CFRP. Eight different heat treatments were applied on five tensile specimens for each. The specimens shape is presented in Figure 2, in accordance with ASTM E8 (diameter 6mm, calibrated length 30mm, ends length 15-20mm, connection radius 8mm, total length 90mm). Quasi-static tests were performed using an INSTRON hydraulic machine, equipped with a 250kN load cell. Strain was measured using a strain gauge from (manufacturer). All the tests were performed with a constant strain rate of 1s-1.

Figure 2: Sample geometry according to ASTM E8.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Printing parameters optimization

For the first step the printing parameters from EOS GmbH – Electro Optical Systems were used to print cubes with dimensions of 20x20x20mm³. These process parameters are suitable for manufacturing components, but may not be optimized for components with very small elements such as the anchors required in this study. A summary of the process parameters is given in the Table 1.

The measured value of density for as-printed specimen was 2.65g/cm³, corresponding to a relative density of 99.38% (theoretical density value of 2.67g/cm³). The initial results of the density required an optimization process.

Table 1: Set of printing parameters from EOS GmbH – Electro Optical Systems.

	Power [W]	Scanning speed [mm/s]	Hatch spacing [mm]	Layer thickness [mm]	VED [J/mm ³]	LED [J/mm]
Infill	370	1300	0.13	0.03	72.98	-
Contour	320	560	-	-	-	0.57

The optimization process consists of two steps: a first step to optimize the parameters for the infill and a second step to optimize the contour parameters. For both phases a Design of Experiment (DoE) methodology was adopted, to investigate many combinations of parameters simultaneously. Small cylinders (diameter of 2 mm and height of 10 mm) were used as reference sample. This choice was dictated by the need of fully dense lattice structure to couple

the additively manufactured metal part with the composite material in the multi-material components.

For the first phase, infill optimization, 27 different sets of parameters were considered (from C1 to C27), from all the possible combinations of the printer parameters listed in Table 2. Three samples for each set of parameters were positioned and distributed along the direction of argon gas flow, as reported in Figure 3.

Table 2: Printing parameters used for the optimization of the infill.

Printing Parameter	Value 1	Value 2	Value 3
Power [W]	370	352	333
Scanning speed [mm/s]	1344	1280	1216
Hatch spacing [mm]	0.124	0.130	0.137

Figure 3: Building plate for the first run of the DoE. Triplets of samples numbered from 1 to 27 correspond to the combinations of printer parameters.

VED values spanning from 60.28 J/mm³ to 81.79 J/mm³ were investigated, granting a minimum relative density of 98.51% for the cylinders. The set of parameters resulting in the highest measured density (>99.99%) was composed by a power of 352W, a laser scanning speed of 1344 mm/s and a hatch spacing of 0.124 mm. The sets of parameters in detail and the resulted relative density for each set are reported respectively in e Table 3 and in Figure 4.

Table 3: Printing parameters and relative density for each parameter set.

Set ID	Power [W]	Scanning speed [mm/s]	Hatch spacing [mm]	VED [J/mm ³]	Average relative density [%]	Standard deviation
C1	370	1216	0.124	81.79	99.92	0.35
C2	370	1216	0.130	78.02	99.59	0.00
C3	370	1216	0.137	74.03	99.19	0.26
C4	370	1280	0.124	77.70	99.33	0.11
C5	370	1280	0.130	74.12	99.42	0.06
C6	370	1280	0.137	70.33	99.19	0.20
C7	370	1344	0.124	74.00	99.59	0.17
C8	370	1344	0.130	70.59	99.46	0.24

C9	370	1344	0.137	66.98	99.22	0.23
C10	352	1216	0.124	77.82	99.29	0.26
C11	352	1216	0.130	74.22	98.82	0.45
C12	352	1216	0.137	70.43	99.79	0.10
C13	352	1280	0.124	73.92	99.62	0.06
C14	352	1280	0.130	70.51	99.42	0.15
C15	352	1280	0.137	66.91	99.49	0.10
C16	352	1344	0.124	70.40	100.27	0.33
C17	352	1344	0.130	67.16	99.89	0.00
C18	352	1344	0.137	63.72	99.62	0.06
C19	333	1216	0.124	73.62	99.39	0.10
C20	333	1216	0.130	70.22	99.25	0.15
C21	333	1216	0.137	66.63	99.52	0.12
C22	333	1280	0.124	69.93	99.59	0.10
C23	333	1280	0.130	66.71	99.76	0.06
C24	333	1280	0.137	63.30	99.79	0.10
C25	333	1344	0.124	66.60	99.79	0.18
C26	333	1344	0.130	63.53	99.08	0.20
C27	333	1344	0.137	60.28	98.51	0.15

Figure 4: Relative density for each parameter set.

For the second phase, the parameters of infill were fixed as the optimum solution in the first phase while the contour was added as investigation parameter. For this second DoE the parameters listed in Table 4 were combined to obtain 9 sets. Three samples for each set of parameters were included and distributed along the direction of argon gas flow, as reported in Figure 5.

Table 4: Printing parameters used for the optimization of the infill.

Printing Parameter	Value 1	Value 2	Value 3
Power [W]	352	320	304
Scanning speed [mm/s]	672	577	560

Figure 5: Building plate for the second run of the DOE. Triplets of samples composing the sets numbered from 1 to 9 correspond to the combinations of printer parameters.

The combinations resulted in LED values range from 0.45 J/mm to 0.63 J/mm. Consequently, relative densities varied from 99.41% to 99.96%. In conclusion, the KPI was achieved for a power of 304 W and a laser scanning speed of 672 mm/s (BC6). The sets of parameters in detail and the resulted relative density for each set are reported, respectively, in Table 5 and in the graph in Figure 6.

Table 5: Printing parameters and relative density for each parameter set.

Set ID	Infill parameters - fixed		Contour parameters		LED J/mm	Average relative density [%]	Standard deviation
	Power [W]	Scanning speed [mm/s]	Power [W]	Scanning speed [mm/s]			
BC1	352	1344	320	560	0.57	99.79	0.48
BC2	352	1344	320	577	0.55	99.48	0.32
BC3	352	1344	320	672	0.48	99.69	0.49
BC4	352	1344	304	560	0.54	99.44	0.66
BC5	352	1344	304	577	0.53	99.81	0.19
BC6	352	1344	304	672	0.45	99.96	0.23
BC7	352	1344	352	560	0.57	99.41	0.22
BC8	352	1344	352	577	0.55	99.69	0.19
BC9	352	1344	352	672	0.48	99.87	0.32

Figure 6: Relative density for each parameter set.

The optimization techniques of LB-PBF on AlSi10Mg increased the density of the printed parts achieving the required specifications for the continuation of the project. That set the foundations for the required mechanical performance of the metal component for joined multimaterial structures in the MIMOSA project.

The synthesis of optimized parameters for the production of AlSi10Mg printed components with high density (above 99.95% of density) is reported below in Table 6.

Table 6: optimized printing parameters for infill and contour.

	Power [W]	Scanning speed [mm/s]	Hatch spacing [mm]	Layer thickness [mm]	VED [J/mm ³]	LED [J/mm]
Infill	352	1344	0.124	0.03	70.40	-
Contour	304	672	-	-	-	0.45

3.2. Heat treatments and tensile tests

The tensile specimens were produced with the optimized parameters. The results intend to provide helpful insights of mechanical and physical characterization of the AM parts subjected in various heat treatments.

The high density achieved due to the optimized parameters should be preserved even after post-printing processes. In particular, density is expected to decrease upon heat treatments application, due to the increase in porosity mainly caused by the formation and growth of Si precipitates that detach from the matrix. However, solution annealing and artificial aging would be needed to obtain uniform performance along different growth directions and increase ductility of printed AlSi10Mg specimens. As shown in the graph in Figure 7, the 3D printed AlSi10Mg joints will have to undergo standard heat treatments and an additional curing cycle during their joining with the composite laminates.

Essential heat treatments include:

- Stress relieving for 3D printed parts: a heat treatment process designed to reduce residual stresses within the material. These residual stresses can develop during the 3D

printing process due to rapid heating and cooling cycles, uneven material deposition, and differences in thermal expansion between layers.

- Solution annealing for AlSi10Mg: a crucial heat treatment process that dissolves the Si network and prepares the material for aging producing the first Si precipitates.
- Artificial aging: enhances the mechanical properties by precipitating a growing finely dispersed particles from a supersaturated solid solution. The process is carefully controlled in temperature and time to achieve the desired balance of strength, hardness, and stability.
- The joining curing cycle; is necessary for the polymerization of the CFRP that will be coupled to the metal anchor in a standard autoclave curing cycle.

Figure 7: Heat treatments T-t curves.

Table 7 shows the different heat treatments. HT6 is the heat treatment described by ASTM F3318 standard, while HT7 is equal to the HT6 treatment plus the standard autoclave curing cycle. The following treatments, HT13 to HT18, involve a change of the parameters of temperature and time in solution annealing and artificial aging. Specifically, for solution annealing treatment it has been noted that, to achieve solubilisation of the silicon network, it is sufficient to reach a temperature of 530°C and maintain it for less than 10 minutes. Compared with the standard treatment, 530°C for 6h, a lower amount of small Si precipitates are created, but the density maintains a higher level. For artificial aging treatments, the temperatures and time parameters relevant for this study are 160°C and 140°C and 360min, 120min and 60min respectively. The treatments from HT19 to HT24 are the same as HT13-HT18 treatments, but with the addition of the autoclave cure at 175°C for 175 min.

The results of the tensile tests and density analysis of the samples are shown in Table 8.

HT6 treatment is standard. There is a stress relieving step to reduce internal stresses due to the printing process. At this stage the solubilisation of the Si network that is responsible for the fragility of as-built parts is already started. This treatment is followed by a solution annealing at 530°C for 6h, which solubilizes the Si, producing many small precipitates. These precipitates are growth in the artificial aging step and are intended to increase the mechanical properties by

blocking the movement of dislocations. The presence of precipitates, however, causes detachment from the matrix, increasing the number of porosities. In fact, the density of HT6 specimens falls below 99%. HT7 treatment has the same heat story of HT6, but autoclave curing was added at the end. This cure acts as additional aging and contributes to the growth of precipitates. This leads to higher mechanical properties than HT6 specimens, but also in this case the density is about 99%.

Because the decrease in density was correlated with the amount of precipitates formed in the solution annealing step, this step was modified from the standard by decreasing the dwell time at the temperature of 530°C from 6h to less than 10 minutes. In this way, fewer precipitates are created, density remains at higher levels, and aging steps (artificial aging + autoclave curing) enhance mechanical performance. In fact, treatments HT13 to HT18 have good densities but much lower mechanical performance. In particular, the mechanical properties of this group decrease with decreasing temperature and artificial aging time.

Adding the autoclave cure, group at HT19 to HT24, results in additional aging treatment, which leads to increase the dimensions of precipitates, bringing the mechanical properties back to the levels of the standard treatment (HT7), but without penalizing the density.

The highest values of Young modulus and yield stress were achieved with the treatments HT7, HT19, HT22. The HT22 is selected as the best heat treatment for the anchors application. This treatment corresponds to the HT16 followed by an autoclave treatment that simulates the curing of the composite part of the joint.

Table 7: Heat treatments on specimens.

Heat treatment	Stress Relieving		Solution Annealing		Quenching in water	Artificial Aging		Fast Air Cooling	Autoclave Curing	
	T [°C]	t [min]	T [°C]	t [min]	t [s]	T [°C]	t [min]		T [°C]	t [min]
HT6	200	120	530	360	30	160	360	yes	-	-
HT7	200	120	530	360	30	160	360	yes	175	175
HT13	200	120	530	>10	30	160	360	yes	-	-
HT14	200	120	530	>10	30	160	120	yes	-	-
HT15	200	120	530	>10	30	160	60	yes	-	-
HT16	200	120	530	>10	30	140	360	yes	-	-
HT17	200	120	530	>10	30	140	120	yes	-	-
HT18	200	120	530	>10	30	140	60	yes	-	-
HT19	200	120	530	>10	30	160	360	yes	175	175
HT20	200	120	530	>10	30	160	120	yes	175	175
HT21	200	120	530	>10	30	160	60	yes	175	175
HT22	200	120	530	>10	30	140	360	yes	175	175
HT23	200	120	530	>10	30	140	120	yes	175	175
HT24	200	120	530	>10	30	140	60	yes	175	175

Table 8: Results from tensile tests and density measurements.

Heat Treatment	Young Modulus [GPa]		Yield Stress [MPa]		Max Tensile Stress [MPa]		Max Deformation [%]		Density [%]	
	Average	Std. dev.	Average	Std. dev.	Average	Std. dev.	Average	Std. dev.	Average	Std. dev.
HT6	70	0.79	223	3.13	281	0.80	16.91	0.67	98.94	0.37
HT7	71	0.15	233	3.09	284	3.55	13.94	0.75	99.09	0.39
HT13	72	0.04	213	2.35	281	3.03	13.18	1.20	99.46	0.02

HT14	73	0.20	153	6.58	242	7.03	22.31	0.31	99.51	0.10
HT15	72	0.21	145	0.90	246	1.09	17.29	1.26	99.58	0.02
HT16	73	0.88	163	16.06	245	10.77	19.64	2.11	99.55	0.17
HT17	73	0.08	138	5.68	233	10.88	22.26	1.04	99.32	0.18
HT18	73	0.27	128	1.26	227	4.90	23.39	2.04	99.33	0.19
HT19	73	0.13	212	15.40	271	10.25	9.58	4.62	99.21	0.04
HT20	73	0.37	203	16.90	265	14.82	11.72	3.50	99.20	0.07
HT21	73	0.16	212	4.89	276	5.00	13.07	1.89	99.11	0.05
HT22	73	0.23	225	2.34	291	1.20	15.51	2.37	99.14	0.07
HT23	73	0.38	207	5.70	270	7.87	13.12	4.37	99.12	0.07
HT24	73	0.27	191	20.53	259	16.83	17.21	3.08	99.23	0.06

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work the developments of joining technologies for aeronautic applications are discussed. High density values were achieved on small-to-medium scale parts upon correction and fine-tuning the printing parameters for bulk production specimens with AM techniques. From the optimization processes, the parameters (hatch spacing, power and scanning speed) that ensure high density for small parts were selected.

An optimization of heat treatments was also carried out: the goal was to maintain a high density and obtain good mechanical properties. This analysis also took into account the autoclave cure that the AlSi10Mg parts will have to undergo to integrate the CFRP.

The mechanical and physical properties of the optimised parts of AlSi10Mg with a LB-PBF process are the stepping stone for the future of AM joining metal-composite technologies in aeronautical sector.

5. REFERENCES

1. De Pasquale et al.. Composite-metal joint based on engineered surface and related manufacturing method. Patent n. IT812019000097134. 2019.
2. De Pasquale. Wing structure based on conformed metallic elements and relative method of construction. Patent n. IT102020000012619. 2020.
3. W.E. Frazier. Metal Additive Manufacturing: A Review. *J. of Materi Eng and Perform* 23 (2014) 1917–1928. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-014-0958-z>
4. A. Gonçalves. B. Ferreira. M. Leite. I. Ribeiro. Environmental and Economic Sustainability Impacts of Metal Additive Manufacturing: A Study in the Industrial Machinery and Aeronautical Sectors. *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 42 (2023) 292–308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.10.004>.
5. H. Ramazani. A. Kami. Metal FDM. a new extrusion-based additive manufacturing technology for manufacturing of metallic parts: a review. *Prog Addit Manuf* 7 (2022) 609–626. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40964-021-00250-x>.
6. M. Xu. H. Liu. X. Bi. Y. Li. Z. Xie. Z. Wang. Developing chemical interaction and achieving mechanical interlock to manufacture high-reliability Polypropylene/A6061-T6 aluminum alloy FAW joints. *Composites Science and Technology* 242 (2023) 110189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2023.110189>.
7. A. Hamilton. Y. Xu. M.E. Kartal. S. Kumar. N. Gadegaard. D.M. Mulvihill. Optimisation of interlocking microstructured adhesive joints via finite element modelling. design of

- experiments and 3D printing. *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives* 120 (2023) 103292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijadhadh.2022.103292>.
8. S. Chowdhury, N. Yadaiah, C. Prakash, S. Ramakrishna, S. Dixit, L.R. Gupta, D. Buddhi. Laser powder bed fusion: a state-of-the-art review of the technology, materials, properties & defects, and numerical modelling. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 20 (2022) 2109–2172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2022.07.121>.
 9. V. Lubkowitz, J. Alber, F. Zanger. PBF-LB Process-Induced Regular Cavities for Lightweight AlSi10Mg Structures. *Materials* 14 (2021) 6665. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14216665>.
 10. P. Moghimian, T. Poirié, M. Habibnejad-Korayem, J.A. Zavala, J. Kroeger, F. Marion, F. Larouche. Metal powders in additive manufacturing: A review on reusability and recyclability of common titanium, nickel and aluminum alloys. *Additive Manufacturing* 43 (2021) 102017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2021.102017>.
 11. EOS website: <https://www.eos.info/en-us/metal-solutions/metal-printers/eos-m-290#key-features>